

EXAMINATION OF FRP FLEXURAL STRENGTHENING OF LOW PERFORMANCE CONCRETE ELEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Many existing structures that were constructed more than fifty years ago are in high probability for being insufficiently designed for earthquake excitation events. Part of those structures include structural wall elements made of low-performance concrete (LPC) as in existing buildings located in the state of Israel and in parts of the Mediterranean area. This paper presents preliminary experimental results performed on authentic and lab-reproduced beam and wall elements to examine the efficiency of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) flexural strengthening of LPC. The test results provide an insight for the efficiency of FRP flexural strengthening of LPC existing elements.

KEYWORDS

Strengthening; Concrete walls; Low performance concrete; Existing structures.

INTRODUCTION

Retrofitting and strengthening existing buildings is becoming a crucial issue around the world. Old low-performance concrete (LPC) structures, which were built without compliance to appropriate building codes and without intention of demolishing them, require significant strengthening due to their outdated design and poor performance. In Israel, a significant number of structures were constructed between 1930 and 1975. Part of these buildings include exterior concrete walls and interior partitions as part of the gravity structural system. These concrete walls are made of unreinforced low-performance concrete (LPC) also known as "Plum concrete". This concrete is characterized by relatively large aggregates (stones that are 100–300 mm in size), a low amount of cement, and a small to zero amount of reinforcement, resulting inferior mechanical properties characterized by significantly lower compressive strength compared with standard concrete. An authentic LPC specimen is shown in Figure 1. Today there is a great awareness of the importance of preservation of old buildings. Most of the existing old buildings from different construction periods are usually retrofitted and renovated gradually for adequate use of today's practices.

Figure 1: Authentic LPC Specimens

There is limited research and studies in the literature about the properties of LPC concrete. This state of knowledge makes it difficult to plan and strengthen buildings constructed using LPC. Previous studies dealt with the quantification of the mechanical properties of LPC concrete (Eid et al., 2021; Ispir et al., 2022). The research of Eid et al. (2021) was based on the extraction of authentic samples of LPC

from existing structures and ones that were cast in the laboratory. The findings allow the evaluation of the tensile strength and the modulus of elasticity of the concrete given the compressive strength. Compression tests were tested on 21 authentic samples, there was a large variance in the compression strength in a range of 3.5-12.2 MPa. This result indicates that LPC is not a standard concrete.

Strengthening solutions of reinforced concrete (RC) members can range from repair of damaged members so that their original load-carrying capacity is restored, to adding elements to increase their strength. One of today's state-of-the-art techniques for retrofitting existing buildings is based on fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites. FRP is increasingly used by structural engineers for rehabilitation of existing structures due to its excellent mechanical properties, for example, high strength-weight ratio, which ease the execution and quick installation. FRP sheets are available in different sizes and shapes and have excellent resistance to corrosion.

Externally bonded FRP technologies are based on the bonding strength between the fibers and the element's surface. It is essential to ensure that adequate conditions in the concrete substrate are being met to allow for strong adhesion to occur (Milev, 2021). Thus, the inferior mechanical properties of LPC concrete (including tension strength) affects the efficiency of strengthening LPC elements. Flexural strengthening of unreinforced low performance (LPC) beams using Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRP) sheets and the effectiveness of the strengthening method will be described in this paper. Laboratory and Authentic LPC specimens are strengthened by externally side bonded carbon FRP sheets as an alternative of steel longitudinal and transverse reinforcement. Results of experimental tests including the effectiveness of the strengthening method on non-standard concrete, failure modes and the flexural capacity of the strengthened elements will be presented in this paper. Moreover, the bending capacity of the tested elements are compared to their analytical capacity which is based on commonly used assumptions.

EXPERIMENTS PROGRAM

Research Methodology

The primary objective of this study is to examine the flexural capacity of strengthened LPC elements using CFRP sheets and to assess the effectiveness of strengthening unreinforced LPC elements. This investigation was carried out in two stages: In the first stage, two laboratory LPC beams were subjected to three-point bending test. This initial stage aimed to examine the feasibility of the method and the failure modes of LPC elements strengthened with CFRP sheets. The second stage involved loading strengthened authentic LPC walls. This stage aimed to further explore the flexural capacity of strengthened LPC elements. The preliminary results obtained from these two stages provide valuable insights into the behavior of strengthened LPC elements.

Specimens details

The experimental research consisted of two stages: the first stage is strengthening and loading two laboratory produced beams with suitable mixture ingredients to best represent authentic LPC. The mixture included large stones (100~300 mm) and the beams were un-reinforced. The preparation and casting of the beams in the lab is presented in Figure 2, and the mixture ingredients of the beams is presented in Table 1.

Figure 2: Casting laboratory LPC beams

Table 1: Mixture ingredients for casting LPC beams

	Volume (L) 1000
	Weight (kg)
Sand	889.4
Small aggregates	945
Large Stones	234
Water	193.6
Cement	111.9
W/C	1.73

The mechanical properties of the LPC beams lead to a low compressive strength compared to standard concrete. The concrete compressive strength of the beams is 9.2 MPa (based on three cylinders 100x200 mm taken from the beam specimens after testing). In order to avoid cracking and failure of the specimens under their own self weight and applying maximum bending moment in order to examine their flexural capacity, a special setup was prepared. Taking into consideration these facts, the specimen consisted of a short LPC element (located in the middle of the beam span) with a limited length of 800 mm and a section of 200x260 mm and two reinforced standard concrete protheses were connected at each side. The specimen of the first stage of the research is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Three-part Specimen from two RC protheses and LPC beam

The second stage presented in this study deals with the preliminary ongoing research of strengthening authentic LPC walls. The results of an authentic wall specimen are introduced in the following chapters. The specimens were carefully extracted from existing buildings and moved to the lab. The extraction procedure is presented in Figure 4. Three cylinders were taken from the authentic specimen in order to determine its compressive strength. The LPC wall of 1200x600x200 mm (height×length×thickness) had a concrete compressive strength of 3.9 MPa. Before applying the FRP strengthening, the wall element was aligned on a specially cast RC base, which was anchored to the strong laboratory floor. This process is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Extracting LPC specimens from old existing buildings

Figure 5: Authentic LPC wall specimen

Strengthening Scheme

The authentic and laboratory LPC beam elements were strengthened using side-bonded CFRP sheets. The special 3-part specimen was strengthened for both flexure and shear. The shear strengthening was applied to ensure flexural failure of the beams. The flexural strengthening consisted of longitudinal sheets applied to the whole length of the beam, the shear strengthening consisted of gluing inclined CFRP sheets at the connection of the LPC beam and the protheses in addition to vertically wrapped sheets that were applied at the connection in order to offer proper anchorage to the longitudinal sheets as shown in Figure 6. The FRP's mechanical porerties are (based on the manufacturer data): modulus of elasticity of 241 GPa, tensile strength of 2866 MPa, and ultimate tensile strain of dry fibers 0.0155 mm/mm.

a) Flexural strengthening of the beams

b) Shear strengthening by inclined sheets

c) Anchorage by vertically wrapped sheets

Figure 6: Strengthening scheme of the beam's specimens

The authentic wall was also strengthened for both flexure and shear. The flexural strengthening consisted of gluing two longitudinal sheets at each side of the wall, four in total. Moreover, three closed horizontal sheets around the wall were applied as shown in Figure 7b. The anchorage of the longitudinal sheets was applied by extending the sheets (to the entire height of the base) and by using FRP spikes at the lower part of the longitudinal sheets as shown in Figure 7c.

a) Flexural strengthening

b) Shear strengthening

c) FRP spike anchorage

Figure 7: Strengthening scheme for the wall's specimen

Test setup

The first stage of the current research was conducted by loading the 3-part specimens by three-point-bending. The specimens were set to the MTS actuator carefully to avoid failure and cracking. The setup is presented in Figure 8a. In the second stage, a strengthened authentic LPC wall was loaded. The wall was placed in a dedicated test setup, which provided the necessary support for the loading process (Figure 8b). The wall was loaded by an in plane horizontal load using a hydraulic jack.

a) Three-point-bending setup

b) LPC wall - test setup

Figure 8: Test setup for the two stages of the research

Measurements

The measurements of the first stage included the applied load and midspan deflection using a 100-kN load cell and a position transducer (POT), respectively. In addition, longitudinal strain gauges were glued at the top face of the beam measuring the compressive strain, and two strain gauges were glued at the longitudinal CFRP sheets at each side (one located at the bottom and the second at 50 mm from the bottom face of the beam) measure the tensile strain of the sheets (four strain gauges in total). Figure 9 shows the measurements taken at the specimen during the experiment. The wall setup included a 250-kN load cell, a POT (to record the deflection of the wall's top corner), and strain gauges (to measure the tensile strains of the horizontal and longitudinal FRP and the compressive strain of the concrete) as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9: Scheme of the measurements of the beam specimens (dimensions in mm)

Figure 10: Scheme for the LPC wall measurements (dimensions in cm)

RESULTS

Failure Modes

The failure of the beam specimens was characterized by the rupture of the CFRP longitudinal sheets. No delamination of the sheets was noticed before the first rupture indicating the good anchorage applied. The rupture occurred initially at the lower most tensioned part of the sheets which gradually progressed into the upper part as shown in Figure 11. This phenomenon corresponds well with the fact that the strain diagram of side-bonded sheets varies through the sheet's height.

a) partial rupture of the lower part of the sheet

b) rupture of the upper part of the CFRP sheet

Figure 11: Failure Modes of the LPC beam specimen

The loading process of the wall specimen initiated cracks at the epoxy resin around the CFRP sheets. As a result of increasing the load, detachment of the horizontal CFRP sheets at the middle of the wall specimen was noticed. Horizontal cracks were detected at the latter location followed by concrete crushing at the lower compressed side of the wall as shown in Figure 12b. The FRP eventually ruptured at the middle of the specimen resulting in a total drop of the load (Figure 12).

a) Detachment of the horizontal sheets

b) Concrete crushing at the lower part of the wall

c) Rupture of the longitudinal sheets

Figure 12: Wall specimen during testing

Load Bearing Capacity

Figure 13 shows the load versus midspan deflection curves for the 3-part specimens. The load consists of the externally applied load and the self-weight. The self-weight of the specimens could not be neglected because of the LPC inferior mechanical properties so the distributed self-weight was converted into an equivalent mid-point concentrated load P_{sw} . The P_{sw} was calculated by two criteria: midspan equivalent moment and midspan equivalent deflection. The values of the self-weight that were obtained according to the two criteria are 2.1 kN and 2.5 kN respectively. The curves in Figure 3 include the distributed self-weight calculated based on criterion of equivalent moment.

Figure 13: Load vs. midspan deflection curves for strengthened beam specimens

Figure 14 shows the load-deflection curve of the strengthened wall specimen. The curve describes the in-plane horizontal load against the deflection of the upper corner of the wall.

Figure 14: Horizontal load vs. top deflection curve of strengthened wall specimen

The results of the 3-part beam specimens show the similar behavior of the two loaded specimens. The load bearing capacity is 20.4 and 20.8 kN for the first and second specimen respectively. The first peak was accompanied by the partial rupture of half width of the CFRP sheets. The second peak was recorded due to the partial rupture of the sheets at the other side of the beam. The sharp drop of the load was due to the total rupture of the sheets. Figure 14 shows that the load bearing capacity of the wall specimen is 115 kN reached after the development of horizontal cracks, crushing of the concrete at the lower corner, and rupture of the FRP.

The experimental moment capacity of the strengthened beams and wall specimens was analyzed. The analytical moment capacity of the beam specimens was evaluated by applying the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory and following these assumptions: 1) parabolic stress-strain relation for the compression of the concrete. This model was employed due to the lack of knowledge concerning the behaviour of LPC, 2) neglecting the tensile strength of the concrete, and 3) linear stress-strain relation for the CFRP sheets. The calculations yielded an analytical moment $M_u = 18.8 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$ and a load bearing capacity of 22.8 kN. The analytical moment agrees well with the measured moment which corresponds with the peaks 20.4 and 20.8 kN of the two specimens, respectively. Proper anchorage of the longitudinal sheets using the vertically wrapped sheets at the connection of the different parts (LPC specimen and RC protheses) prevented the delamination of the sheets. Rupture of the longitudinal sheets determined the failure mode of the two beam specimens. The maximum tensile strain that developed at the longitudinal sheets was smaller than the strain reported by the manufacturer (Salama et al, 2019; Shahawy et al, 1996) . The preparation of the second stage set up was executed according to the results of the first stage. The longitudinal sheets were anchored using the horizontally wrapped FRP which was used mainly for shear and by using FRP spikes applied to the specially cast foundation. The longitudinal sheets failed due to rupture. In addition, their maximum tensile strain did not exceed the manufacturer's reported strain as well.

Special care was granted to the development of the shear cracks. The analytical shear capacity of an FRP-retrofitted concrete element comprise of the concrete shear capacity and the contribution of the horizontal FRP sheets. Due to the relatively small concrete compressive strength (~4 MPa) the contribution of the concrete to the shear capacity was neglected. In addition, the overall shear capacity is limited by the compression capacity of the inclined concrete struts. Thus, the failure mode of the strengthened concrete elements can be controlled by this capacity. Based on the CSA S806 (2012) this capacity is 97 kN. Moreover, the analytical moment of the wall specimen was estimated according to

the rectangular stress block assumption for the concrete in compression and the FRP tensile strain was based on the results of the beam specimens. The in-plane analytical horizontal force derived from the analytical moment capacity is 108 kN. The aforementioned analytical loads support the conclusion that the failure was due to a combined failure of bending and shear.

The reported results are limited to two beam specimens and one wall specimen. Considering the small number of specimens tested, cautious has to be considered. Further specimens will be tested to examine the effectiveness of using CFRP sheets as a strengthening method for non-standard concrete.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents preliminary experimental results performed on authentic and lab-reproduced beam and wall elements to examine the efficiency of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) flexural strengthening of low-performance concrete (LPC). Unreinforced LPC is characterized by relatively large aggregates (stones that are 100–300 mm in size), a low amount of cement, and a small to zero amount of reinforcement, resulting in inferior mechanical properties compared with standard concrete. The research was divided into two stages: 1) The first stage comprised of loading two laboratory LPC beams using three-point bending test. This stage was considered as an initial stage for the purpose of learning the behavior and failure modes of strengthened LPC elements using carbon FRP sheets. 2) The second stage involved loading of strengthened authentic LPC wall. The preliminary results show that flexural strengthening of LPC elements is feasible considering their limited bonding and shear capacities.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.